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Physiological Metrics for Adult and Younger Users Based on a Cognitive Analytical Modeling

History

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Introduction

Cognitive workload has been shown to make a negative impact on user performance in different tasks that demand a high amount of mental workload. Cognitive load mostly refers to the amount of load placed on the users and their working memory (Sepp *et al.* [1], Chen *et al.* [2]). The importance of measuring cognitive workload has been well explained in past research due to its applicability in various contexts such as multimedia, automation, problem-solving and instructional design. Cognitive load can be measured and monitored in real-time as a process to capture the automation and experience of the user. The accurate measurement of the cognitive workload can be applicable in mitigating strategies for adaptation of user interface in response to changes in cognitive assessment (Hudlicka and Mcneese [3], Akoumianakis *et al.* [4], Machado *et al.* [5], Schneider *et al.* [6], Duric *et al.* [7], Rosman *et al.* [8]). The most standard approach is presenting a stimuli complexity to both average

and above users were below average lies in the range of average users. This technique is necessary because this differentiates the level of how each of these users views a presented stimulus so that the result obtained can be used to optimise the process from average response to high ratings and reduction of failures.

Abstract: Recent research has seen that cognitive load has been widely studied to help in understanding user performance. Here we propose a framework for monitoring and detecting the cognitive load of users by a non-invasive measure with a multimodal physiological sensor that records eyes-to-skin surface reaction. Fifty-five participants were recruited and engaged in a task that induced slightly different cognitive responses ranging from stress to relaxed mood. The result shows that the cognitive response was predicted based on control motor dynamics that can accurately detect user behavioural patterns with little error of 0.01%. This also outperforms previous work and shows the reliability of the proposed model.

Keywords: Multimodal measuring sensors, Cognitive load, Model Framework, Physiological data, Human-computer interaction

It is very important to monitor user cognitive load in applications such as Human-computer interaction (HCI) and Robotics, to achieve operational safety and improvements to usability and user experience; this would subsequently allow for efficient workload and management for the avoidance of user error. On the hand, tracking user cognitive load in real-time is often difficult when the aim is achieving higher accuracy. Here we propose a framework for monitoring and detecting the cognitive load of users by a non-invasive measure with a multimodal physiological sensor that records eyes to skin surface reaction. Fifty-five participants were recruited and engaged in a task that induces slightly different cognitive responses ranging from stress to relaxed mood. The task is to identify natural patterns in an already predefined cognitive response using residuals from user behavioural data.

Literature Review

The concept of cognitive load management is that it plays a crucial role in improving our learning processes. The part of the brain that is responsible for this is the “working memory”, but it also can only remember little information or can process a large amount of information (*Goldman-Rakic [9], Klingberg [10], Ricker et al. [11], Jonides and Smith [12], Shrager et al. [13], Carlesimo et al. [14], Smith and Jonides [15]*). For this purpose, there is a need for well-defined strategies to optimise the limited capacity of the working memory for deriving an engaging and efficient learning process. The main concept is to distinguish what goes into the model to be improved and goes out without any disruption to the learning processes (*Christensen [16], Jiang et al. [17], Levin [18], Watkins and Wagner [19], Soriano-Pascual et al. [20], Hudlicka and Mcneese [3]*). Research has seen that there are three types of cognitive load, these are Intrinsic load (inherent complexity of the learning material), Extraneous load (impediments to learning and cognition), and Germane load (facilitating effective learning process). The cognitive load in theory is built upon the widely accepted model of user information processing (Figure 1) (*Paas et al. [21, 22]*), where the process has three main parts such as sensory memory, working memory, and long-term memory. Most research seeks to add to this concept and optimise memory speed based on its strategies. The framework adopted for this paper uses a multimodal measuring sensor to access user cognitive load with eye movement patterns based on control motor dynamics.

Method

The method adopted for this research is based on an experimental study where Fifty-five users (30 adults and 25 younger participants) were recruited for the study. They were asked to sit in front of a PC (Figure 2) with a webcam that calibrates their eyes to the visual screen. During the task, they were asked to place their hand on a multimodal sensor that is embedded with Skin conductance response (SCR) and Skin temperature (ST). The pupil response was measured by the webcam port that registers the eyes and records every pupil change and the response as it moves on screen.

0.1 Task

The task is to try and identify natural structures in an already predefined dataset, where the results or resultant residual is the view through a stalactite plot. Natural structures are identified by the occurrence of outliers consecutively. All the residual outputs present the data have outlying on till the most outlying cases are detected and the same order is followed for subsequent outliers. Natural patterns are usually seen to be close together and

have similar color (Figure 3), while unnatural patterns are distinct with different patterns.

The aim is to locate these similar patterns with the same color and count the number of similar structures and color that are close together. This procedure requires concentration and an amount of effort that induces a cognitive response from the users that fall into the categories of “stress”, “relaxed” and “neutral” mood. The latency for response detection is based on a hand-clap signal to determine a baseline to response states that could be tonic or phasic change from the participants. The cognitive response based on eye movement related to pupil constriction and dilation can signify stress or relaxation. The pattern generated can be classified using pattern recognition by the control motor dynamics in the proposed model (Figure 4)

Data is generated from the experimental setup and simulated to two thousand sets for both training and supervised methods. The user attributes are selected from important features used to determine users cognition in most studies (*Younas et al. [23], Greisdorf and O’Connor [24], Smith and Andrews [25]*). Such as the SCR baseline, ST, Pupil response, and fixation location. Feature extraction is done in a supervised manner by the control motor dynamics. The cognitive state is classified as stress, relaxed, and neutral mood. The neutral mood can also fall within the range of relaxed or stressed mood depending on the cognitive level of the user that falls below and above the baseline estimate. The result of the analyses is discussed in the results section below.

Result

Figure 5a and 5b, show the aggregate of fixation location in the diagram of natural structures detected in the behaviour data. The residuals are used to differentiate similar patterns with colors that enable the user to identify the natural patterns in the data. The physiological response obtained shows that the cognitive state of the children is usually high if they try to find these patterns and shoots down low when such patterns are identified. The excitement and eagerness also contribute to the pattern identification and spikes in their physiological responses.

Figures 5c and 5d show the eye movement patterns and physiological response of middle-aged participants where the SCR seems to move in synch with the ST and Pupil changes. The spikes are detected with a low-level baseline. This makes it quite difficult to detect a phasic change in their physiological response which is in contrast to the older participants. The older participants’ response data shows a similar pattern to the middle age group and the difference is the increase in SCR baseline that indicates a significant response to the natural patterns compared to younger participants.

Figure 1: Information processing model on memory optimisation

Figure 2: Participants sit in front of a PC with an embedded webcam that calibrates eye movement to the visual scene while their physiological response is monitored wirelessly with a multimodal sensor.

Conclusion

The method in this paper seeks to investigate in real-time the cognitive load of users based on identifying areas with high and low cognitive processes from the participants. The task is to identify natural patterns in an already predefined cognitive response using residuals from user behavioural data. The results show that older participants were able to identify natural structures in the data-presented stimuli with a stress reaction, while younger participants identified natural patterns in the data with slight stress. The cognitive response was predicted based on a control motor dynamic that can accurately detect user behavioural patterns with little error. The future perspective of the work is to compare the models' accuracy with other standard techniques like SVM, Decision Tree, and Naive Bayesian methods.

Figure 3: Index stimuli for users' response to natural structures in data.

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Figure 4: The proposed Framework model, with user stimuli elicitation and feature extraction.

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(a) Eye movement (Fixations) on Children participants to natural structures in data.

(b) Physiological response of Children participants to Visual stimulus.

(c) Eye movement (Fixations) of Middle age participants to Natural patterns in data

(d) Physiological response of Middle-aged participants to visual stimulus.

(e) Eye movement (fixations) of Older

(f) Physiological response of Older participants to visual stimulus.

Figure 5: Aggregate response of Participants to Identifying natural structures in data in synch with their physiological response